

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B152
Date: 17 Dec 2005
Take Off: 11:06:15
Landing: 15:39:54
Flight Time: 4h33m39s

Campaign: CAESAR / CIRRUS / SWS
Operating Area: Chilbolton 253 radial

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Jonathan Taylor	Met Office
5	Flight Manger	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
7	Drosondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
8	MARSS/DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
9	Drosondes u/t	Paul James	FAAM
10	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
11	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
12	CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
13	TAFTS	Paul Green	ICL
14	TAFTS	Maxwell Bolton	ICL
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B152
 Date: 17 dec 2005
 Project: SWS test
 Location: SW approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
102436		INU	-.20 kft	256	to NAV
105406		start	-.20 kft	256	50'43.95N 003'24.81W gps
110615		T/O	1.2 kft	066	Exeter
110757		asp	1.5 kft	062	open
111220	120615	Profile 1	1.7 - 32.0 kft	078	
111341		video	3.0 kft	061	#1 dfc, #2 rfc
112652		interrupt P1	18.0 kft	057	
112733		overhead Chilbolton	18.0 kft	043	
113442		overhead Chilbolton	18.0 kft	272	westbound
113735		restart P1	18.0 kft	272	
114950		interrupt P1	28.0 kft	267	f1280
115012		video	28.0 kft	267	recycle titler
115515		restart P1	28.0 kft	050	
120421		contrail starts	31.6 kft	060	
120555		overhead Chilbolton	32.1 kft	039	
121231	123628	Run 1.1	32.0 kft	274	f1320
121408		abeam Chilbolton	32.0 kft	294	
121430		bbr	32.0 kft	298	retracted
121752		video	32.0 kft	298	#2end,#4started rfc
122014		turn onto radial	32.0 kft	296	
122230		wings level	32.0 kft	267	
123736		heimann	32.0 kft	344	cal
123801		Nev	32.0 kft	018	zero
124051	124209	Run 1.2	32.0 kft	088	
124155		video	32.0 kft	079	#1end,#3started dfc
124225	125824	Run 1.3	32.0 kft	063	
125534		sonde 1	32.0 kft	060	
125824		overhead Chilbolton	32.0 kft	047	
130744	131332	Run 1.4	32.0 kft	268	positioning for orbit
131345			32.1 kft	281	reboot fm pc
132223		!	32.0 kft	266	end chilbolton work
131400	131718	orbit 1	32.0 kft	265	30' f1 320
131722	132044	orbit 2	32.0 kft	265	30' f1 320
132646		video	32.1 kft	265	#4 end #6 start
132717		!	32.0 kft	265	#6 is rfc
134551		transit	32.0 kft	262	to orbit location
134827	135012	Run 2.1	32.0 kft	307	dodecagon
135056	135259	Run 2.2	32.0 kft	338	345
135347	135559	Run 2.3	32.0 kft	005	015
135633	135835	Run 2.4	32.0 kft	033	045
134700		video	32.0 kft	033	#3 end ,#5 start dfc
135925	140124	Run 2.5	32.0 kft	063	075
140205	140412	Run 2.6	32.0 kft	093	105
140453	140653	Run 2.7	32.0 kft	127	135
140734	140935	Run 2.8	32.0 kft	160	165
141024	141224	Run 2.9	32.0 kft	196	195
141307	141506	Run 2.10	32.1 - 32.0 kft	228	225
141552	141752	Run 2.11	32.1 - 32.0 kft	258	255
141834	142037	Run 2.12	32.0 kft	283	285
142154		contrails	31.3 kft	284	engine test stopped
142537	142542	Run 3	26.1 - 26.0 kft	034	
142837		video	26.0 kft	030	#6 end #8start rfc
142900	143902	Run 3.1	26.0 kft	029	f1 260
143924		Heiman cal	26.0 kft	042	
143945		nev	26.0 kft	077	zeros
144258	145300	Run 3.2	26.0 kft	212	f1 260
145106		video	26.0 kft	214	#5 end #7 start dfc
145722	145759	Orbit 1	26.0 - 26.1 kft	348	60'
145858	150039	Orbit 4	26.1 kft	182	150 established
150141	150307	Orbit 5	26.1 - 25.9 kft	087	established 065

150435	150606	Orbit 6	26.1 - 26.0 kft	030 established 060
150656	150828	Orbit 7	26.1 - 26.0 kft	101 establish 120
151537		!	26.0 kft	336 end science
153954		Land	-.22 kft	094 Exeter
154510		gps	-.22 kft	242 50'43.93N 003' 24.81W
154613		inu	-.22 kft	242 50'44.43N 003' 28.41W

B152 Track 17-DEC-05

CAESAR SORTIE BRIEF

Cirrus in-situ measurements for radar validation

B152 17th December 2005

Aim

The aim is to study the in-situ properties of cirrus over land, co-ordinated with the Chilbolton radars/lidars

Weather

Cirrus, ideally with clear skies below. Some cloud below is acceptable, as long as the cirrus is measurable by the radar.

Operating region

Runs and profiles are expected to take place along a fixed radial from the Chilbolton Meteorological Observatory (51 08' 36" N 01 26' 02" W) at the location of the cirrus, ideally into and with the wind direction. Note, the 35GHz radar and lidar have a fixed vertical view and hence measurements directly over the site are critical. Only the 3GHz is steerable during CAESAR 1.

Clearances

Clearances will be required for dropping sondes and performing a profile from minimum allowable altitude.

Communications

With operators at Chilbolton via SATCOM or VHF radio (130.575 MHz, call-sign "Radsearch").

Sortie for Cranfield takeoff

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	12:00	Takeoff from Exeter		0
2	12:00	Transit at appropriate level to enter operating area at min altitude	10	10
3	12:10	Profile ascent from minimum altitude to cloud top at 1000ft/min or to max altitude	40	75
6	12:50	1 straight and level run above cloud. Drop 1 sonde.	10	170
7	12:58	Satellite overpass during run.		
8	13:00	Reciprocal straight and level run.	10	180
9	13:15	Perform a series of reciprocal straight and level runs at several levels within, below and above the cloud, into and with the wind direction ideally along a Chilbolton radial, with profile descents between each level. Orbits may be flown at the end of runs below the cirrus cloud if airspace restrictions permit.	80	260
10	16:30	Profile descent to min altitude at 1000ft/min	30	290
11	17:00	Transit to Exeter	10	330

Requirements for ARIES and SWS

In the cloud:

ARIES: nadir with calcs every 2 minutes ideally during turns

SWS: series of approximately 0, 180, 90 and 45 degree viewing angles during every run with appropriate calcs (measurements to be used to test Robin Hogan's 3D stochastic model) - see extra guidance sheet.

Above cloud:

1st run above cloud

ARIES & SWS both viewing nadir. Calibrations to be coordinated such that both instruments simultaneously view the cloud for the maximum time.

2nd run above cloud

ARIES & SWS both viewing nadir **then** for last 2 minutes both viewing zenith .

Mission Scientist's Debrief

Flight B152 17th December 2005.

Jonathan P Taylor.

The aim of this flight was to study thin cirrus overhead Chilbolton radar and then to conduct some SWS tests in the SW approaches.

On take off from Exeter a stepped profile was flown along the 253deg radial towards Chilbolton. The profile was interrupted at FL180 to go overhead Chilbolton and then resumed on a SW heading. The profile was interrupted again at FL280 near Exeter and resumed on a heading towards Chilbolton. The observatory was overflown at FL320. The aircraft began contrailing at FL315. Overhead Chilbolton there was no cloud at low level and all the cirrus was above FL320. At no time during the sortie were we able to penetrate the cirrus clouds. From the radar it could be seen that aircraft passing overhead were 5000ft higher and still contrailing, it was also evident that there was cirrus above these higher aircraft.

To the SW end of the runs there was extensive boundary layer cloud but this remained clear of Chilbolton for the entire sortie.

A series of three runs at FL320 were flown passing the overhead of Chilbolton with the final run culminating with an AIRS overpass at 12:58 and ARIES, SWS and TAFTS all looking up through the cirrus cloud as the 146 passed directly over Chilbolton a dropsonde was launched over the New Forest on the final run in before the overpass. After the over pass we re-positioned to the SW of Chilbolton to give sufficient airspace to conduct some orbits. A series of orbits with 30 degree angle of bank were then flown.

This concluded the cirrus part of the sortie and the 146 then transited to the SW approaches to find some clear skies to conduct some SWS tests.

Having found a suitable operating area in the SW Approaches a Dodecagon (12 sided pattern with 30degree turns between each run) was flown at FL320 with the SWS looking upwards. The skies were clear above for this series of 12 runs.

The aircraft then descended to FL260 for a couple of runs down and in to sun. There may have been some thin Ci during some of these runs. After these runs five orbits were flown with 50 degrees of bank. This concluded the SWS tests.

Summary

The cirrus overhead Chilbolton was extensive but optically very thin and all above the aircraft. A good overpass of AIRS was coordinated with a run above Chilbolton with SWS, ARIES and TAFTS making zenith views.

The SWS tests should prove useful in understanding the internal reflection problems with the SWS.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. TAYLOR

Flight No **B.152**.....

Date 17/12/05.....

Page 1 of 39

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110903					T/OFF
111220	P1	20000ft			stg P1 along 253° radial towards Chilbolton 5 ⁵ SC over Exeter but deep
					good w/put thin Ci overhead
111700					clear below thin Ci above.
112046		FL110			thin Ci overhead some a/cpt containing clear skies below
112652	P1	FL180		51.1/14	Intercept P1 to go overhead Chilbolton Swth to SWcy
112730		FL180			Overhead Chilbolton thin Ci above clear skies below.
113440		FL180			Overhead Chilbolton thin Ci above.
113735	P1	FL180A	292	51/1.8W	Restart P1 TWC does not work at the moment.
114357		FL234			TWC is now working
114730				over	Blky layer clear now some vws structure visible.
	P1	FL280			Intercept Angke turn back towards Chilbolton.
115515	P1	FL280↑	058	50.8/2.9	Restart P1 back towards Chilbolton.
115816		FL285			T = 73°C Td = 63.4°C.
120200		FL310.			T = -50°C. GE = -47.7 FWSS = 44°C.
120438		FL315			Stabd to control. 96.9 75.9 90.0 5.4

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50°50'N
1°40'W.

Flight No **B.152**.....

Date **17/12/03**.....

Page **2** of **39**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
120615	R1	FL320			End of R1 was <u>workload</u> Chilton Still containing. 120645. 120555
					No imagery on ZDC or CPI just below Ci base
121231	R1.1	FL320	275	50.8/12	Stop Run back to SW. Not workload Chilton turn was power limited so we ended up way to South.
121345			299		Aircraft above ~ 5000ft containing Top of Ci at least above FL370. No chance of us getting above it Still no imagery on ZDC or CPI Still containing.
122025					Change of heading to recapture 253° radial back to SW. Eastern Ci above clear below at Chilton b'ding longer to SW end of run.
122157		FL320	266		Wings level. Extended run to SW
123036					Over SE now. to engine workload Chilton on next run at 1715 and pass time.
123628	R1.1	FL320	264	50.6/4.3	End Run 1.1
124051	R1.2	FL320	087	50.7/39	Stop Run 1.2 Interrupt R1.2
124225	R1.3	FL320	063	50.7/37	Interrupt R1.3 now on heading per workload Chilton

225° 3/16

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Flight No **B.152**.....

Date 17/12/05.....

Page 3 of 39

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
124619		FL320			still contacting 91.0 NI
					726 TGT
					8804 WZ
					4.9 FF/FA.
125035					clear & cloud below now 8/8 Ci ahead
125533	R1.3	FL320	060	51/1.8	Depende launch. 1. SWOS, ARIES + TRAPS
					holding up for ARIES
					was pass.
					* ARIES was pass 12:58. ✓✓
125822					overhead Chubbston
125824	R1.3	FL320			End of R1.3
130744	R1.4	FL320	268		step R1.6 reposition down track to SW of Chubbston to find clear airspace probat.
131332	R1.6	FL320			End R1.6
131345	01	FL320		50.9/2.6	step 01 30° bank
					Then Ci ahead. - looks clear
					still contacting but not persisting. then it did for ARIES was pass.
131718	01	FL320			End of 01
131722	02	FL320			step 02 30° bank appears to be thinning rapidly
132044	02	FL320			End of 02
	DAVE P LOBS NOW				Dodecagon runs in SW approaches
	PRIMARY MISSION SCIENTIST.				clear skies above - Sc below.
					We are continuing at FL320
					except at FL300 is not continuing
					except - at FL360 is continuing = non persistent

*Very hot
Possibly some of thin Ci
worked during
down sun run at FL260*

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Rollman

Flight No **B.152**.....
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Date *17/12/5*.....

Page *1* of *6*...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:06					Take off
					into ~ 2/4 Cu/Sc @ various levels
11:12:20	P1	2000	79		Still below bases
		3000			starting to come level w/ some bases. Under more layered cloud.
11:15:00					Cloud thinning as we progress W.wards
11:15:45					Now very clear passed edge @ ~ 5-7 hft Some Cir Ci above
11:17:20					Passed over some lenticular cloud
11:19					V. clear below, some scat. Cu bit of high
	P1	180	57	57.101.5W	Interrupt
11:27:30					Overhead Chilton
11:34:45					" "
11:39:30			287		Seem to have resumed profile
11:45					ci thickening up overhead at this end.
11:46					
11:46					Extensive St/Sc below and to west now.
	P1	280	267		Interrupt.
					Some thin Ci out to W. over 2/4 Sc, not much above.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Pollock

Flight No **B.152**.....

Date*17/12/5*.....

Page *2* of *6*

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:53					Edge of Sc below
11:55:50	P1	280	50	50.8N 2.8W	Per start of profile
12:02		315	60		Just starting to contract Ci above appearing slightly thicker
12:05:45					overhead distillation
21					
12:06:00	P1	320		51.1N 1.3W	end of profile
12:08					Contrails getting stronger
12:09					Ci here seems a lot thicker
12:12	R1.1	320	275	50.9N 1.1W	Ci way above Still contracting
					Ci base appears to be at least 5 kft below
12:20:15					Turning back onto radial
12:22:09		268	266		Wings level.
12:28:45					Coming over cloud edge for Sc Extending run to be over distillation for 12:58 set overpass.
12:36:28	R1.1	320		50.63N 4.41W	Still contracting
12:37					Low cloud more broken to N
12:40:57	R1.2	320	87		
12:42:09	R1.2				END
12:42:25	R1.3	320	62	50.72 -3.69	Start of run.
					Still contracting

Received

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...152**.....
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Date17/12/5.....

Page ...3... of ...6....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:47		320	62	50.86 N 7.06 W	Still contracting, still Ci above ~ 1/8 So below (just crossed main edge)
12:55:34					Sound # 1
12:58:23	R1.3	320			Over Chilton, end of run & Aqua overpass.
13:07:44	R1.4	320	265	51.08 ~ 1.8 W	Start run to pos. for orbit 3. Still Ci above, clear below still contracting.
13:13:	R1.4	320			End
13:13	O1	280 →	280		Start of 30° orbit to right Still contracting
13:17	O1		280		end orbit 1
13:17.23	O1	300	300		start orbit 2 Contrails still being produced but not persisting v-long
13:20:43	O2				end of orbit
13:24:46		50.74 N 3.1 W			Crossing lower cloud edge
13:32					Still contracting, not persisting slightly weather than before
13:48:12	Z1 O1		315		start of Redacted
	Z2		336		
13:52.59	Z2	320			End
13:53:47	Z3		004		Start

post-d

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**...132.....
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Date17/12/5.....

Page ...4. of ...6....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:52:14					A/c at +1900 ft cont'd on
					" at -1900 ft cont'd
					We are trailing
13:55:	2.3				End not persistent
13:56:	2.4	320	045	50.9 N 6.31 W	Start
13:					
13:58:35	2.4	320	045		End
13:59:25	2.5		075		Start
					Clear above more so
					to 5 km N.
14:01	2.5		10		End
14:02:	2.6		105		Start
14:04:02	2.6				End
14:04:53	2.7		135		Start
14:06	2.7				End
14:07:32	2.8		165		Traffic is at -1900 ft
					not trailing
					We trailing
14:09:35	2.8				Traffic at +6000 ft trailing
					more persistently
14:10:22	2.9		195		Start
14:12:24	2.9				End
14:13:07	2.10		225		Some Ci ahead rolling
					above

Aircraft Scientist's Log

W PMA

Flight No **B.152**.....
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Date17/12/5.....

Page ... of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Traffic at + 6000ft trailing
14:15:06	2.10				End
14:15:52	2.11		253		Start
14:17:12	2.11		284		End
14:18:32	2.12		283		Start
14:20:37	2.12				End power off and stopped trailing
					Slow inc in power
14:21:22					Just started 370 kph/min
14:29:00	3.1	260	30		Start of 100k run
					Clear above, some Ci ahead
					NA trailing, settings
					81.8 / 640 / 84.3 / 4.3
14:37:44					Might be coming under some thin Ci
14:39:	3.1	260			End of run down on
14:43.00	3.2	200	212		Start of run into sun
14:48					Clear above, pass at bit of thin Ci ahead
14:50					Thin Ci ahead did to left
					QNH 1013
14:52	3.2				End of, still looks clear above

13/11/08

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...152**.....
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Date17/12/5.....

Page **6**..... of **6**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:56					Positioning α and inc.
14:57					speed for 60° orbits Turn Ci to left
14:57:20	03				
			130		not possible to hold 60°
	04	260	130		50° bank left Clear above
	04				End
	05	260			50° bank left Turn Ci to S.
	05	260			end
15:06					Still turn Ci to S
	06	260	060		50° Right orbit
15:06	06				end
					Still turn Ci
15:07	07	260	120		50° bank to right Sun is coming through Ci
15:08	07				Complete
15:15					End of Science.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B152

Date: 17/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 11:54:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:12:24	150	0.08	0	10	10											Start profile 1 from 2000'	
11:13:41	65	0.08		10	8											FL030	
11:14:33	55	0.08		10	5											FL040	
11:15:34	70	0.09		5	1											FL050	
11:16:25	20	0.09		2	1											FL060	
11:17:24	7	0.08		1												FL070	
11:18:06	15	0.08		1												FL080	
11:18:54	10	0.07														FL090	
11:19:48	12	0.08														FL100	
11:20:42	1	0.05														FL110	
11:21:36	1	0.05														FL120	
11:22:31	1	0.05														FL130	
11:23:32	1	0.06														FL140	
11:24:09																FL150	
11:24:48																FL160	
11:25:41	1	0.05														FL170	
11:26:42	1	0.06														FL180	
11:38:48	1	0.06														FL190	
11:39:51																FL200	
11:40:58	2	0.06														FL210	
11:42:03																FL220	
11:43:07	1	0.06														FL230	
11:44:24	2	0.06														FL240	
11:45:42																FL250	
11:47:06					Noise											FL260	
11:48:26	Noise				Noise	Noise										FL270 SID2 File 10 to Uni	
11:49:49	Noise				Noise			Noise								FL280 Rearm 2 1	
11:57:35	Noise							Noise								FL290	
11:59:32	Noise					Noise		Noise								FL300	
12:02:09	Noise					Noise		Noise								FL310	
12:06:15	Noise					Noise		Noise								End of Profile 1 @ FL320	
12:12:29																Start Run 1.1 @ FL320	
12:13:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
12:15:00	Noise					Noise		Noise								Rearm 1 1	
12:17:00	Noise				1	Noise		Noise									
12:19:00	Noise				5	Noise		Noise									
12:21:00	Noise				1	Noise		Noise									
12:23:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
12:25:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
12:27:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
12:29:00	Noise				Noise	Noise		Noise									
12:31:00	Noise				Noise	Noise		Noise									
12:33:00	Noise				Noise	Noise		Noise									
12:35:00	Noise				Noise	Noise		Noise									
12:36:28																End of Run 1.1	
12:40:50																Start Run 1.2 @ FL320	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B152

Date: 17/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 11:54:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:41:00	Noise		0		Noise	Noise		Noise									
12:43:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
12:45:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
12:47:00	Noise							Noise									
12:49:00	Noise							Noise									
12:51:00	Noise							Noise									
12:53:00	Noise							Noise									
12:55:00	Noise							Noise									
12:57:00	Noise							Noise									
12:58:22																End of Run 1.2	
13:07:25																Start Run 1.3 @ FL320	
13:08:00	Noise							Noise									
13:10:00	Noise							Noise									
13:12:00	Noise					Noise		Noise									
13:13:29																End of Run 1.3	
13:13:45																Start Orbits	
13:20:42																End of Orbits	
13:48:40																Start Run 2.1 @ FL320	
13:49:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
13:50:12																End of Run 2.1	
13:50:55																Start Run 2.2 @ FL320	
13:51:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
13:52:59																End of Run 2.2	
13:53:47																Start Run 2.3 @ FL320	
13:54:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
13:55:51																End of Run 2.3	
13:56:34																Start Run 2.4 @ FL320	
13:57:00	Noise							Noise									
13:58:33																End of Run 2.4	
13:59:24																Start Run 2.5 @ FL320	
14:00:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
14:01:22																End of Run 2.5	
14:02:05																Start Run 2.6 @ FL320	
14:03:00	Noise							Noise									
14:04:05																End of Run 2.6	
14:04:52																Start Run 2.7 @ FL320	
14:05:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
14:06:52																End of Run 2.7	
14:07:37																Start Run 2.8 @ FL320	
14:08:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
14:09:33																End of Run 2.8	
14:10:26																Start Run 2.9 @ FL320	
14:11:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
14:12:24																End of Run 2.9	
14:13:06																Start Run 2.10 @ FL320	
14:14:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B152

Date:17/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 11:54:00	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:15:08			0													End of Run 2.10	
14:15:54																Start Run 2.11 @ FL320	
14:16:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
14:17:52																End of Run 2.11	
14:18:33																Start Run 2.12 @ FL320	
14:19:00	Noise							Noise									
14:20:38																End of Run 2.12	
14:29:00	Noise				Noise			Noise								Start Run 3.1 @ FL260	
14:31:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
14:33:00	Noise				Noise			Noise									
14:35:00	Noise							Noise									
14:37:00	Noise							Noise									
14:39:02																End of Run 3.1	
14:43:00	1	0.06						Noise								Start Run 3.2 @ FL260	
14:45:00	2	0.06			Noise			Noise									
14:47:00	1	0.06			Noise			Noise									
14:49:00	5	0.06			Noise			Noise									
14:51:00	1	0.06			Noise			Noise									
14:52:58																End of Run 3.2	
14:57:24																Start Orbits	
15:08:49																End of Orbits	
PCASP noisy at high altitudes PCASP Flowrate = 1CC/sec SID2 Noisy at times 2D2-C Noisy at high altitudes 2D2-P Noisy at high altitudes																	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B152**Date:** 17/12/2005

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B152.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B152.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B152.zip		
6) In PVWAVE		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B152.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B152_seadas.dat iii) exit	10/04/06	51060 blocks read/written Zero bad reads
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE		Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B152 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B152_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	10/04/06	Data ends after 152400
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional
Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B152 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B152 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10		Both probes are largely noise data throughout
iv) exit PVWAVE	Creates files	PMSDATA: FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B152_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B152 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B152_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B152_PROC2D		If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. Note the particle type Not processed due to noise dominance
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B152_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B152_M5PROC2D' iii) exit		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B152_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B152_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B152

Date: 17/12/2005

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures B152_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW		Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
a) Flight number: B152		
b) File name: PMSDATA:B152_FSP.DAT		
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:B152_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:B152_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:B152_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)		
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	1	
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	1.0	
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	0	
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	110000	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	154700	
3) In PVWAVE		Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!		
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B152_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:B152_m5procpcasp'		
iii) exit	10/04/06	
4) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B152_m5procpcasp		
b) Datset: mfddata:B152_mfdX		
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	MFDB	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	10/04/06	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B152**Date:** 17/12/2005

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:B152_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B152.nc]	10/04/06	As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B152.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B152.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_B152_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary	10/04/06	

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:B152*. * outdir:B152_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.	10/04/06	Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B152**Date:** 17/12/2005

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC B152_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B152_FFSSP_HVMS.txt B152_FFSSP.raw B152_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B152_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS B152.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (B152.zip) - rename B152.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B152_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B152_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_B152_rawseadas.zip	10/04/06	Binary data transfer

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	17/11/05	Flight	B152	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CAESAR			
Departure	EXT		Arrival	EXT			

System start MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on				at time	09:06:38		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	54°C	Ch	58°C	Ch18	40°C	
Temperature controller set points		7.2°C	17	7.2°C	-20	7.2°C	
MARSS CPU on				at time	09:09:09		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	277.9	Cold	277.9			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	09:10:55		
Scan indication			Monitor)	Visual	X	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Start Deimos Software				at time	09:13:44		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	277.4	Cold	277.4			
Target heating							X
Scan indication			Monitor)	Visual	X	
Weather	Cloud	7/8 Cu/SC	Precip	No			
	Surface	5.32	Pressure	1020			
	Other						

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$		at time				
Brightness temps 'sensible'							X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.51	Cold	280.9		
	Deimos:	Hot	344.83	Cold	289.06		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	1	1	1	1			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	22.09	35.29	36.22	37.33	40.67		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B152	Date	17/12/05		Operator(s)	Ian Rule	log page	of
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks		
				Vis	NIR			

0920			Zen	200	500	SWS on checked ok, box temp = 10		
110613			90R	200	500	T/o Exeter, dark cal made		
111220	P1	2000'	Zen +6 F	200	500	Start run, SWS operating ok		
111808	P1		"	"	"	Start tape recording count = 0:00:00		
112652	P1	FL180	"	"	"	Interrupt		
113735	P1	FL180	"	500	1000	Restart, clear above		
114950	P1	FL280	"	"	"	Interrupt, poss some thin Ci above		
115516	"	"	"	"	"	Restart. Some stray light evident in SWS tube during turn before restart of run.		
1202	"	FL310	"	"	"	Some Ci showing on camera		
120615	P1	FL320	"	"	"	End profile, dark cal in turn		
121231	R1.1	FL320	"	"	"	Start run, thin Ci above, box temp = 13		
123630	R1.1	FL320	"	"	"	End run, dark cal in turn		
124052	R1.2	FL320	"	"	"	Start run, box temp = 12, thin ci above		
124209						Interrupt run		
124225	R1.3	"	"	"	"	Restart, box temp = 12 thin ci above		
125825	R1.3	"	"	"	"	End run, followed by dark cal		
130744	R1.4	FL320	"	"	"	Start run		
1313						End run		
131400	O1	"	"	"	"	Start orbit, 30 deg RHD		
131718	O1	"	"	"	"	End orbit		
131722	O2	"	"	"	"	Start orbit		
132044	O2	"	"	"	"	End orbit, dark cal at end, box temp = 14		
1324		"	"	"	"	Thin ci above, temp = 14		
1342		"	"	"	"	Prob clear above, box temp = 14, dark cal		
134826	R2.1	FL320	Zen+6F	500	1000	Start run dodecagon, sample period 1s		
135012						End run		
135056	R2.2	"	"	500	500	Start run, sample period 500ms		
135301						End run, box temp 14		
135349	R2.3	"	"	"	"	Start run		
135553						End run		
135624	R2.4	"	"	"	"	Start run		
135835		"	"	"	"	End run, box temp = 14		
135925	R2.5	"	"	"	"	Start run		
140124						End run		
140206	R2.6	"	"	"	"	Start run, box temp = 13		
140407						End run		
140454	R2.7	"	"	"	"	Start run		
140654						End run		
140736	R2.8	"	"	"	"	Start run		
140936						End run		
141025	R2.9	"	"	"	"	Start run		
141225						End run		

ARIES flight log		Flight: B15L	Location: EXETER	page 1	of
Date: 17/12/05	Operator(s): Joss Kerr.	Resolution: low	Gain A: 2	B: 2	
Notes: Skills on problems with scan rate dropping					

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
0930	STARTED FLIGHT RECORDING									
095200	Grnd	B152A	Clsd						N1	1st run long. Included data at trigger
095525	" "	B152B	Clsd	71.2	30.9				N1	
095649	" "	B152D	Clsd	71.0	31.1	23.0	190.6	23.0	Z1	1st run long. " " "
095845	" "	B152E	Clsd	71.1	31.1				CH1	1st run long.
100017	" "	B152F	Clsd						CH2	100200 almost 2 runs
100949	FLIGHT RECORDING STOPPED									
1056	Grnd	Set CBB to 10°C from 30°C								
1113	CBB temp only dropped to 25°C - set it to 20°C									
111500	Third setting gain to 1 on Chan B. gain too high so left it on 2.									
112600	Scan rate dropping down to 60 s/run. Set it to 236 s/run for a non memoryless									
113225	P1	B152G	Clsd	70.9	22.2	3.3	189.9	24.4		1st cal. started to run slow near end of cal.
114051	P1	B152H	Clsd						test	
	P1	B152I	Open						Z1 x 2	
	Rise PC to see if the scan rate settles down.									
113634	Started recording									
115840	P1	B152I	Clsd	71.0	22.5	3.2	189.9	20.3		
	P1	B152J	Open							
120644	P1	B152J	Clsd	71.2	22.8	4.4	189.9	16.4	CH2	Cal before run start

1258'

ARIES flight log

Flight: B15Z

Location: Chababron

page 2 of

Date: 17/12/05

Operator(s): Joss

Resolution: 1cm¹

Gain A: 2

B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Sht	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
121230	R1-1	B15Z K	Open	69.8	22.0	-23.8	-189.9	12.9	Z1 x 3	F1520.
121545	" "	B15Z L	Clso	71.1	22.5	-			CH2 x 1	
121816	" "	B15Z M	Open	70.6	22.2	-22.3	-189.9		Z1 x 3	F1320.
122137	" "	B15Z N	Clso	70.7	22.6	-27.0	-190.6		CH2 x 1	
122402	" "	B15Z O	Open	70.9	21.8	-26.2	-189.9	11.0°C	Z1 x 3	At end of run.
122719	" "	B15Z P	Clso	71.0	22.7	-26.3	-190.6	8.4°C	CH2 x 1	
122949	" "	B15Z Q	Open	70.5	22.0	-25.5	-190.6	11.3	Z1 x 3	Extended run
123304	" "	B15Z R	Clso	70.9	22.3	-25.6	-190.6	11.0	CH1 x 1	steady if quicker cal worked
1234??	" "	B15Z S	Clso	70.8	22.6	-25.2	-190.6	12.9	N1 x 2	Just because I can.
123640	End R1-1	B15Z T	Clso	70.8	22.6	-26.5	-190.6	14.0°C	CH1	In turn.
124051	R1-2	B15Z U	Open	66.7	22.4	-26.1	-190.6	16.6	Z1 x 3	F1320 - some banking at start
124411	R1-3	B15Z V	Clso	71.0	22.4	-26.2	-190.6	10.8°C	CH2	
124630	R1-3	B15Z W	Open	70.5	22.2	-26.6	-190.6	13.3	Z1 x 3	
124940	R1-3	B15Z X	Clso	70.8	22.5	-27.6	-190.6	8.0	CH2	
1252??	R1-3	B15Z Y	Cl/op	71.7	22.1	-26.5	-190.6	13.1	Z1 x 3	Shutter closed at start
125516	R1-3	B15Z Z	Clso	71.0	23.1	-27.4	-190.6	11.3	CH2	
125933	R1-3	B15Z 0	Open	70.8	23.1	-27.1	-190.6	15.0	Z1 x 3	End of run before finished
130043	R1-4	B15Z 1	Clso	75.7	22.5				CH2	
130659	-	B15Z 2	Clso	71.2	22.0	-26.0	-190.6	16.6	CH1	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B152

Location: Chobolmen

page 3 of

Date: 17/12/05

Operator(s): Joss

Resolution: 1cm

Gain A: 2

B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
130714	R4	B1523	open	68.9 70.8	22.6	22.4	48.9	.	Z1 x 3	
131045	" "	B1524	closed	71.6	22.2	22.4	-190.6	8.9	CH2	
131353	Obort 1	B1525	open	70.3	22.8	22.9	-190.6	13.9	Z1 x 2	
131607	" "	B1526	open	70.4	22.3	22.4	-190.6	7.6	Z1 x 2.	
131830	Obort 2	B1527	closed	70.8	22.6	22.3	-190.6	7.9	CH2	
132518	-	B1528	closed	70.2	22.4	22.9	-190.6	18.7	Z1 CH1	
132737	-	B1529	closed	70.8	22.3	22.0	-190.6	18.7	N1 x 3	
133036	-	C152A	closed	70.7	22.5	22.8	-190.6	15.6	CH1.	
133224	see CH2 gain vol 4									
133732	Reset gain on CH2 vol 2									
1340	Problems still with scan rate - getting worse Reset PE - but problem still here.									
1400	Left ARIES off for 30 mins. - Redundant. - Problem still here. smash/hud C1523 closed. 70.5 22.7 19.6 19.8. 12.8 CH2 [though not so bad.									

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 152**

Date: 17th December 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JN02	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JN02	Y	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	Y		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B152

Date: 17th December 2005

Instruments

1. SID 1 – working
2. PCASP – noisy at times
3. 2D-P noisy at high level
4. 2D-C noisy at high level
5. FSSSP ok
6. SID 2 working, some noise
7. Flight Manager's PC – locked up 13:14:00 Rebooted, then okay.
8. TAFTS working
9. ARIES working – scan problem
10. SWS working ok
11. MARSS ok, no channel 16
12. CPI working
13. JW zero pot is set to nearly full scale (fully clock), zero now stuck off scale (-ve)
14. CO signal noisy, reported by Joss & Paul

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B152:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing - now available for partial data:	Raw FFSSP is incomplete - this may have been a recording problem during the flight. Also the 2D probes continue to generate essentially noise. Phil Brown has just processed the PCASP data and included this in the core-cloud-phy_NetCDF file uploaded to BADC. There's a possibility he may still be able to do something more with FFSSP on B152.
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
TAFTS	No log is ever taken for TAFTS

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x forward Facing Cameras

4 x forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

Manager Atmospheric Radiation Research Group
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 884647

Fax: +44 (0)1392 885681

E-mail: jonathan.p.taylor@metoffice.gov.uk